

Psychological Peculiarities of Personal Dissonance of Adolescents in the Sphere of Real and Ideal Self-Image

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Abstract: *Adolescence is characterized by contradictions of role behaviours and perceptions caused by age adjustment of adolescents. This is reflected in the system of self-attitudes of adolescents, which can lead to intrapersonal conflicts due to the dissonance of conceptions about their own real and ideal self-image. Such dissonances can hinder the construction of one's own social roles. Therefore, timely detection of risks of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of subjective perceptions of one's own real and ideal self-images becomes one of the leading tasks of providing psychological and psychotherapeutic aid to adolescents, aimed at harmonizing their formation in the process of socialization. The aim of the research is to study the factors that determine the psychological peculiarities of personal dissonance of adolescents in the sphere of real and ideal self-image. The research is based on the use of psychodiagnostic methods of Leary (2004) and Pantileev (1993) for the survey of 303 adolescents of both sexes at the age of 14-17, who recognize the presence of discrepancies between real and ideal self-images. Empirical data has shown a relationship between a constellation of psychological factors that determine the emergence of personal dissonances in the sphere of authoritarianism, dominance, suspicion, aggression, subordination, dependency, friendship and altruism. The research will help to understand the psychological factors of the emergence and functioning of personal dissonances of adolescents, which affect both the system of their self-attitude and the building of their social ties. This opens up prospects for improving psychoprophylactic measures aimed at preventing personal dissonances in adolescents.*

Keywords: *personal dissonance; adolescents; self-image; self-attitude; individual and psychological qualities; psychological factors.*

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1. Introduction

The problem of adolescence has always attracted the attention of scientists because of the complex and intense transformations of the individual during the transition from childhood to adulthood. The crisis phenomena that occur during this period are associated with the restructuring of both socio-role statuses and the relevant conceptions of the adolescent. Radical changes in adolescents' perceptions of themselves as they enter the adult world often accompany the emergence of complex psychological problems. Such problems can interfere with adequate socio-psychological adaptation, socialization, as well as the emergence of various deviations, ranging from self-destructive behaviour and ending with delinquent manifestations.

Changes in perceptions of oneself, as well as rethinking one's own current and desirable self-images in the future can occur relatively harmoniously. In this case, maturation occurs without crisis shifts. Conversely, significant discrepancies between real and ideal self-images can lead to dissatisfaction, intrapersonal conflicts, and, as a consequence, violations in the sphere of self-attitude (Tsilmak et al., 2020). Such discrepancies between the ideal and real self-image in the adolescent's imagination create personal dissonance both on the cognitive and emotional levels. That is why, it is necessary to understand the factors that may affect the emergence of personal dissonance in order to effectively provide psychological aid to adolescents in cases of crisis experiences in the process of moving into adulthood.

Many researchers have studied the phenomenon of dissonance from different angles since the work of Festinger, who first introduced this concept into scientific circulation, explaining intrapersonal conflict situations that arise in the mind of an individual (Festinger, 1962). The works, which conceptually try to highlight the origins of this psychological phenomenon take attention analysing the main approaches, in the context of the topic of our research.

For example, Cooper tries to analyse the relationship between personal dissonance and socio-psychological phenomena (Cooper, 2019). From our point of view, this approach is important, because the formation of conceptions about oneself and its role in adolescents in the process of socialization becomes the basis for the development of characterological psychological qualities. At the same time, the significant transformations of the self-image that occur in the process of socialization are related to the correlation on the one hand, of external expectations from the reference

environment of the adolescent, and on the other hand – their own formed conceptions and priority expectations of themselves. This is where, firstly, the formation of reflection takes place, due to which the adolescent's self-esteem develops his own present image, and secondly, the conception of the image he seeks to approach in the future. And this is where the reason for the possible dissonance lies. If the image of the self-real and the self-ideal do not have fundamental discrepancies, then the person is formed more harmoniously. If there are significant discrepancies between the real and the expected desirable images of oneself, it can cause intrapersonal conflict due to the dissonance of these conceptions.

The age characteristics of adolescents are determined by the fact that they come out of childhood and enter adulthood. In such a case, some roles inherent in a child die out, and a young person must master the roles inherent in adult life in their place. As Maziar points out, the process of internalization, i. e. the assimilation of new behavioural patterns, is always associated with the process of exteriorization, as the ability to actualize these acquired behavioural patterns, knowledge, skills and abilities in one's own life (Maziar, 2020). Therefore, it is important for a teenager to not only learn certain forms of adult behaviour, but also the ability to restructure himself so that they do not remain declarative, but become immanent to him. There may also be a source of dissonance, if the assimilation of images of adult roles and the corresponding psychological qualities and character traits, leads to a contradiction of too stable conservative images of children's behaviour. Such an inability to moving into adulthood causes a conflict between the current adolescent and the desirable personal image, which may be the cause of infantilism.

A similar position is taken by Hagège and colleagues, who prove that the presence or absence of the ability to reconcile images can be a source of dissonance in the individual (Hagège et al., 2018). And due to the fact that adolescence is the most controversial period of life, when age crises occur and the demands of moving into adulthood meet with the capabilities of the adolescent, it is natural that the risk of personal dissonance increases during this period due to inconsistencies in social roles and self-images.

The process of transformation of old self-images with new ones, in the context of reorganization of personal constructs was considered in detail by Naccache, El Karoui and other scientists who studied personal dissonances through the prism of human ability to subjectively correlate different, including contradictory, conceptions and images (Naccache et al., 2015). It can be assumed that this ability is directly related to the adaptability of the individual, and more adaptive adolescents are easier to adapt to the

new requirements of the self-image of an adult in the future, internalizing them in the relevant neoplasms of their own personal constructs. In addition, less adaptive adolescents face the difficulties of such a restructuring, as a result of which there are significant contradictions between real and desirable self-images, resulting in the risk of personal dissonance. At the same time, defects of adaptability block the ability to overcome personal dissonance, which deepens the crisis on the background of intrapersonal conflicts. This situation, according to Harmon-Jones, is a negative reinforcement, which further exacerbates the level of personal dissonance (Harmon-Jones, 2000).

No less important is the role of adolescent self-attitude. Thus, overestimated or underestimated self-esteem, violation of self-identification, loss of self-worth also complicate a teenager's self-acceptance. And, according to Stone, the reflexive potential of the individual plays an important role in this process, which allows him to build adequate self-esteem, correlating it with his own standards and conceptions (Stone, 2003). Otherwise, the defects of reflection create an even greater inconsistency of perceptions of oneself, and, as noted by Klein and McColl, trigger even greater cognitive distortions of self-image against the background of the inclusion of psychological mechanisms of unproductive self-defence (Klein & McColl, 2019). Therefore, we will pay special attention in our research to the analysis of the relationship between the dissonance of self-images and the system of self-attitudes of adolescents.

The emergence of dissonance due to the violation of the adaptive potential of the individual can lead to the inability of the adolescent to learn the social norms that must be followed by every adult. According to Van der Velden and colleagues, this leads to social maladaptation, which, due to the lack of moral standards, results in antisocial behaviour of adolescents (Van der Velden et al., 2010).

Similar dysfunctionality may be associated with adolescent empathy shortcomings. As a result, as Laughy and co-authors emphasize, there is a so-called empathic dissonance, which disrupts the process of adequate socialization and building productive relationships with others (Laughy et al., 2021).

The inability to correlate one's own real and ideal self-images causes significant stress in the adolescent. According to the research by Davis, Panksepp and Normansell, they increase the vulnerability of adolescents to destructive psychological phenomena acquiring a negative affective colouration (Davis et al., 2014). In addition, such a discrepancy of self-images, as noted in the work of Aleksandrov and Okhrimenko increases the

risk of neurotic disorders in adolescents on the background of personal dissonance and intrapersonal conflict (Aleksandrov & Okhrimenko, 2020).

Conversely, the adolescent's ability to harmoniously construct the vector of transformation of the current real self-image into the expected desirable ideal image of himself in the future adult life gives him confidence. Such confidence is accompanied by positive emotional reinforcement, which, as Robins and co-authors point out, increases the adolescent stress resistance and, consequently, minimizes the risk of dissonance emergence (Robins et al., 2012).

However, considering adolescence, Alessandri and colleagues emphasize that personal dissonances can have not only a negative connotation, as they can also stimulate personal growth (Alessandri et al., 2008). In this case, they can encourage the adolescent to revise his own conceptions about the self-image, and, as E. Harmon-Jones and C. Harmon-Jones emphasize, activate the adaptive potential in the direction of finding ways or approaching the real self-image to the ideal one, or approximation of the idealized image to a more realistic one (Harmon-Jones & Harmon-Jones, 2020). In addition, as we noted above, the readiness to overcome internal crises that have arisen due to the dissonance of self-images, inspires a person to self-change. As a result, there is an increase in self-confidence, which turns out, as evidenced in the studies by Cancino-Montecinos and colleagues, to be a factor in reducing the severity of personal dissonance (Cancino-Montecinos et al., 2018). And, as Braun, Schmidmaier and other scientists note in their works, it becomes possible to build psychotherapeutic and preventive programs on this basis in order to provide psychological aid to adolescents (Braun & Schmidmaier, 2019; Cancino-Montecinos et al., 2020).

Of course, these scientific developments do not exhaust all the variety of modern approaches to the study of the nature of personal dissonances, but allow us to determine the vector of our empirical research. In view of the above, to study the psychological peculiarities of personal dissonances in adolescents it is necessary to investigate the relationship of conceptions about real and ideal self-images, which determine, on the one hand, strategies for building interpersonal relationships, and on the other hand – the system of the adolescent's self-attitudes and his self-image.

The aim of the research is to study the factors that determine the psychological peculiarities of personal dissonance of adolescents in the sphere of real and ideal self-image.

2. Methodology

To solve the tasks in hand we have selected relevant psychodiagnostic tools, which made it possible to investigate the manifestation of personal dissonance and the corresponding changes in the system of self-attitudes in adolescents, which arose due to mismatch of conceptions about their real and ideal self-image.

1) the method of the Interpersonal Diagnosis of Personality of Leary (Leary, 2004). This methodology is designed to study the conceptions of the individual about his real and ideal "Self", and contains the following scales aimed to diagnose: 1) authoritarianism; 2) egocentrism; 3) aggression; 4) suspicion; 5) subordination; 6) dependency; 7) friendship; 8) altruism.

2) the method of the study of self-relationships (the attitudes towards oneself) "MSS" of Pantileev. This methodology was used to determine the deformation of the adolescents' perceptions of their own "Self-image", and contains the following scales aimed to diagnose: 1) sincerity; 2) self-confidence; 3) self-control (self-management); 4) demonstrated self-attitude; 5) self-worth; 6) self-perception; 7) self-attachment; 8) intrapersonal proneness to conflict; 9) self-blame (Pantileev, 1993).

The psychodiagnostic techniques used in our study are not original. They are adapted versions in Russian and Ukrainian, the use of which is authorized by Ukrainian scientists on the basis of a cooperation agreement between G. S. Kostiuk Institute of Psychology of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine and international public professional organization European Federation of Psychologists Associations (EFPA) (No. 27/134 dated 12.05.1997).

The empirical basis of the research consisted of 303 adolescents at the age of 14-17 (164 males and 139 females), the preliminary results of whose study revealed signs of dissonance and corresponding changes in the system of self-attitude. The research was conducted in secondary schools and psychological centres of Kyiv (Ukraine) in 2020-2021, processing and interpretation of the results was conducted at the Department of Social Work, Faculty of Psychology, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (Kyiv, Ukraine) and the Department of Legal Psychology of the National Academy of Internal Affairs (Kyiv, Ukraine).

Based on the tasks of the research, we conducted a mathematical and statistical analysis of the main correlation relationships of indicators of manifestation level of personal dissonance of the real and ideal self-images in adolescents according to the method of Leary (2004) and indicators of self-

attitude system according to the method of Pantileev. In the course of processing, the existing relationships were determined by calculating Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. This is due to the fact that the metrics obtained are not subject to the law of normal distribution. It should be noted that concerning the sample size ($n = 303$), the statistical value of r_s is not less than 0.113 with $p \leq 0.05$, the high value of r_s is not less than 0.149 with $p \leq 0.01$, and the maximum value of r_s is 0.189 with $p \leq 0.001$.

The study was approved by the Ethics Commission in accordance with the university community code of ethics, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (3.1). Informed consent was obtained from all participants; they were able to withdraw the study at any time. Also, the research was performed according to the requirements of the Regulations on Academic Honesty at the National Academy of Internal Affairs, which were developed on the basis of Ukrainian and world experience of ethical rulemaking. This document was approved by the Academic Council of the National Academy of Internal Affairs (Protocol No. 5 of 27.03.2018 and implemented by the order of the Rector of the Academy (Order No. 422 of 30.03.2018. According to its provisions, the members of the scientific community are guided by the rules of ethical conduct and professional communication; respect the principles, values, norms, rules, and conditions of academic honesty in their activities. The consent to participate in the study was obtained from all subjects.

3. Results

Let's start our research with the analysis of the average values of the self-real and self-ideal indicators according to the Leary method (2004). This allows us not only to describe subjective perceptions of our current and expected future priority personal characteristics, but also to identify discrepancies between these images. And it is precisely these discrepancies that point to the non-coincidence between the real self-image and the one the adolescent would like to have. These discrepancies cause the presence of more or less pronounced dissatisfaction with the self-image, and, accordingly, personal dissonance (Table 1).

Table 1. Average indicators of the self-real, the self-ideal and differences between them according to the Leary method (2004)

Researched indicators	Self-real	Self-ideal	The discrepancy between the real and the ideal self-image
Authoritarianism	9.47	11.30	+1.83
Egocentrism	7.42	8.16	+0.74
Aggression	8.05	7.16	-0.89
Suspicion	7.27	4.82	-2.45
Subordination	7.23	5.32	-1.91
Dependency	7.84	6.64	-1.2
Friendship	8.63	9.16	+0.53
Altruism	8.99	9.31	+0.32

As it can be seen from the table, authoritarianism, as the desire for a certain dominance, occupies the leading place in adolescents in real self-esteem. The second and the third places are taken by altruism and friendship, as conscious humanistic values. The fourth place is occupied by aggression, but due to the insignificant expressiveness of the scoring weight, it can be argued that it is important for assertiveness in defending one's own interests and willingness to resist external dangers and obstacles. A moderately distinguished indicator of dependence occupies the fifth place, which can be pronounced in the form of obedience and caution due to lack of life experience and the preservation of the principles of child discipline instilled in the upbringing of parents and teachers. As we can see the sixth place is taken by a weakly pronounced egocentrism, which is a natural phenomenon in adolescence associated with building one's own boundaries in the process of emancipation. The seventh place is occupied by a weakly pronounced indicator of suspicion, which may be associated with a certain distrust of the new adult life and adult interactions within the system of social relations in which the adolescent is gradually immersed. And the last eighth place is occupied by the indicator of subordination, which indicates the gradual emancipation of the adolescent from the adults' dictate.

As for the assessment of the desirable ideal self-image, adolescents have a similar situation, but some qualities are wanted by them as more pronounced, and others, on the contrary, less pronounced. Thus, the first three positions in the desirable image of adolescents are preserved for authoritarianism, altruism and friendship, and it should be emphasized that they would like to have them even more pronounced. They would also like to have a more pronounced manifestation of egocentrism in their own

character as an element of self-affirmation. Instead, adolescents would like to reduce indicators of aggression, dependency, subordination, and suspicion as interfering with normal self-perception.

On the basis of comparative analysis, we can observe those characterological peculiarities that cause some adolescents' dissatisfaction with themselves and can lead to personal dissonance. In particular, the greatest discrepancy between the real and the desired ideal self-image is observed in the indicators of suspicion, subordination, authoritarianism and dependency. This is where a significant source of dissonance can lie, because it is these qualities that adolescents want to change the most in themselves. Less pronounced are the discrepancies between the real and the desirable self-image in terms of aggression and egocentrism. These qualities, although weak, but are still pronounced, and therefore can also be considered a potential source of self-dissatisfaction, and, consequently, albeit small, but still, the risk of dissonance. And the least pronounced are the discrepancies in the field of friendship and altruism, which indicates sufficient satisfaction of adolescents with the current level of development of these qualities.

The next step in our research is to analyse the average profile of the system of self-attitudes of adolescents, which may indicate harmony or disharmony of the individual in the system of adolescents' self-satisfaction or self-dissatisfaction (Table 2).

Table 2. Average indicators of self-attitudes according to the Pantileev method

Researched indicators	Sincerity	Self-confidence	Self-management	Demonstrated self-attitude	Self-worth	Self-perception	Self-attachment	Intrapersonal proneness to conflict	Self-blame
Average score	5.98	7.53	6.46	6.45	8.08	6.89	6.09	5.02	4.65

It should be noted that according to the Pantileev method (1993), the optimal indicators are in the range of 3-6 stens. The indicators that deviate significantly towards the minimum scores indicate the problem of self-attitudes due to the insufficient manifestation of this quality. Conversely, the indicators that deviate to a greater extent show the problems of self-attitudes due to excessive aggravation of these qualities. It is excessively low

self-attitude or hypertrophied self-attitude that becomes a sign of personal disharmony, which is associated with personal dissonance. Therefore, we will start from those qualities that deviate more from the norm in the sequence of the description.

Based on the expressiveness, it is possible to state a significant excess of the norm in terms of self-worth indicator, which indicates a tendency of adolescents to overestimate the value of their own personality.

The indicator of self-confidence is the next most expressively growing one, which can be explained by inflated self-confidence in terms of one's own strengths and capabilities due to the lack of real life experience, which would allow adolescents to realistically and more adequately assess their potential. Next, it is worth noting the moderate increase in self-perception indicator, which may be associated with insufficient self-criticism due to underdeveloped reflexive abilities, as a result of which the adolescent tends to accept himself and even justify his shortcomings. However, a moderate overestimation of self-management indicates a certain tendency to hyper control, which may be associated with self-affirmation in the eyes of others as a person with developed self-possession. The indicator of demonstrated self-attitude indicates this desire for self-affirmation, which is also slightly overestimated in the life of the adolescent, and can be explained by the desire to create a favourable impression of himself in the eyes of others. These tendencies in some way correspond to the tendencies to a certain egocentrism we have identified above, which accompanies adolescent emancipation against the background of tendencies to self-affirmation. Other indicators (self-attachment, interpersonal proneness to conflict and tendencies of self-blame) are within the norm and therefore do not require special attention, because we have described the indicators that deviate, and thus may be associated with disharmonious tendencies of personal dissonance of adolescents.

However, the description of the average profile of psychological factors of personal dissonance of adolescents does not allow to fully identify those of them that are directly related and in some way cause this destructive phenomenon. Therefore, the next step of our research will be a correlation analysis of the discrepancy indicators between the perceived real and desirable self-images, as a source of personal dissonance of adolescents, with their other psychological characteristics (Table 3).

The table presents the correlations that show the significant relationships between each of the possible manifestations of personal dissonance of adolescents with other psychological factors. Given the rather large number of significant correlations that can be seen in the table, when

describing the results, we will refer only to the most significant ones, which correspond to the maximum levels of reliability $p \leq 0.001$ and $p \leq 0.01$. We determine the sequence of description based on the assessment of the significance of discrepancies between the real and desirable self-images of adolescents, which we presented above when interpreting the results of Table 1. It should be noted that correlation analysis showed the greatest number of significant relationships in dissonance indicators within the sphere of suspicion (17), subordination (18), authoritarianism (15) and dependency (13). This confirms our assumption that these spheres of personal dissonance have the greatest impact on other psychological constructs of adolescents.

Therefore, let us start with the dissonance indicator in consequence of suspicion due to the desire of the adolescent to reduce it. Thus, the greatest relationship was found with the indicator of suspicion of the perceived current real self-image ($r_s = 0.623$, $p \leq 0.001$), which means the adolescent's dissatisfaction with his problems associated with excessive mistrust. Next in importance is the indicator of propensity to self-blame ($r_s = 0.282$, $p \leq 0.001$), which shows the adolescent's feeling of distrust to himself.

Table 3. Correlations of dissonance indicators with indicators of the self-real, the self-ideal and discrepancies between them according to the Leary method (2004), as well as indicators of self-attitudes according to the Pantilev method (1993)

Researched indicators		Indicators of dissonance							
		Authoritarianism	Egocentrism	Aggression	Suspicion	Subordination	Dependency	Friendship	Altruism
Indicators of self-real	Authoritarianism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Egocentrism	0.552	0.194	0.063	0.140	0.310	0.146	0.185	0.035
	Aggression	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Suspicion	0.246	0.311	0.008	0.087	0.217	0.173	0.010	0.009
	Subordination	0.160	0.057	0.237	0.088	-	0.012	-	0.007
	Suspicion	0.118	0.222	0.161	0.623	0.222	0.154	0.031	0.098
	Subordination	0.300	0.167	0.047	0.279	0.589	0.278	0.074	0.111

	Dependency	0.125	0.045	0.036	0.205	0.200	0.425	-	0.102
	Friendship	-	-	-	-	0.088	0.186	-	-
	Altruism	0.009	-	-	0.086	0.076	0.099	-	-
Indicators of self-ideal	Authoritarianism	0.044	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Egocentrism	-	-	-	-	-	0.075	-	-
	Aggression	-	-	-	-	0.048	0.019	-	-
	Suspicion	-	0.115	-	-	0.038	-	0.019	-
	Subordination	0.020	-	-	0.051	-	-	0.069	-
	Dependency	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Friendship	0.040	-	-	-	0.026	0.040	-	0.002
	Altruism	-	-	-	0.070	-	-	-	0.018
Indicators of dissonance	Authoritarianism		0.205	0.095	0.231	0.354	0.177	0.212	0.165
	Egocentrism	0.205		0.089	0.198	0.257	0.245	0.098	0.070
	Aggression	0.095	0.089		0.218	0.139	0.053	0.194	0.128
	Suspicion	0.231	0.198	0.218		0.265	0.225	0.258	0.247
	Subordination	0.354	0.257	0.139	0.265		0.393	0.173	0.254
	Dependency	0.177	0.245	0.053	0.225	0.393		0.104	0.220
	Friendship	0.212	0.098	0.194	0.258	0.173	0.104		0.377
Altruism	0.165	0.070	0.128	0.247	0.254	0.220	0.377		
Indicators of self-attitude	Sincerity	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Self-confidence	0.062	0.051	0.087	0.057	0.049	0.069	0.028	0.079
	Self-management	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Demonstrated self-attitude	0.091	0.169	0.080	0.177	0.197	0.148	0.081	0.122
	Self-worth	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Self-perception	0.183	0.139	0.110	0.253	0.258	0.180	0.130	0.169
	Self-worth	0.210	0.139	0.093	0.112	0.090	0.119	0.065	0.110
	Self-perception	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		0.120	0.162	0.040	0.110	0.067	0.059	0.065	0.029

Self-attachment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.190	0.145	0.044	0.181	0.181	0.163	0.037	0.022
Intrapersonal proneness to conflict	0.134	0.077	0.011	0.221	0.233	0.178	-	0.040
							0.054	
Self-blame	0.174	0.087	0.041	0.282	0.272	0.232	-	0.082
							0.027	

Next indicator is the indicator of subordination of the real self-image ($r_s = 0.279$, $p \leq 0.001$), which determines the adolescent's awareness of distrust of his social status due to excessive susceptibility to influence from others and adults in particular. This corresponds to the following significant correlation with the indicator of personal dissonance in the manifestation of subordination ($r_s = 0.265$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is also a source of internal dissatisfaction. Similarly, suspicion is associated with the indicator of dissonance in the manifestation of friendship ($r_s = 0.258$, $p \leq 0.001$), when the adolescent is worried about possible failures in close social ties. The relationship between suspicion and the indicator of demonstrated self-attitude ($r_s = -0.253$, $p \leq 0.001$) can be explained by the fact that attempts to position oneself in a favourable image become a protective reaction to others, who may pose a potential threat to his status. This mistrust can be explained by the following important relationship with the indicator of dissonance in the manifestation of altruism ($r_s = 0.247$, $p \leq 0.001$), when the adolescent may fluctuate between the manifestation of openness and altruism and distrustful distance. This causes a feeling of insecurity, which causes fluctuations in the manifestations of one's own protective dominance, as indicated by a strong correlation with the indicator of dissonance in the manifestation of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.231$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such excitement is determined by the internal dissonance of the feeling of self-dependency, as indicated by the following important relationship ($r_s = 0.225$, $p \leq 0.001$), which corresponds to discomfort due to the adolescent's awareness of such excessive dependency and in his own real self-image ($r_s = 0.205$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such suspicion against the background of uncertainty leads to contrasting tendencies, which gives rise to an increase in intrapersonal proneness to conflict ($r_s = 0.221$, $p \leq 0.001$), which can lead to feelings of dissonance due to dissatisfaction with one's own aggression ($r_s = 0.218$, $p \leq 0.001$) and egocentrism ($r_s = 0.198$, $p \leq 0.001$), which can cause a violation of productive and meaningful for the adolescent social ties. Attempts to get rid of such suspicion are confirmed by the next most important correlation with the indicator of suspicion of the ideal self-image ($r_s = -0.188$, $p \leq 0.01$), the

inverse nature of which indicates a desire to reduce it in himself. Also, dissonance on the background of suspicion causes a decrease in the indicator of self-confidence ($r_s = -0.184$, $p \leq 0.01$), self-attachment ($r_s = -0.181$, $p \leq 0.01$) and self-management ($r_s = -0.177$, $p \leq 0.01$), which makes the adolescent vulnerable to the risks of neuroticism and other destructive psychological consequences. However, on the other hand, trying to reduce self-suspicion will lead to increased self-confidence, self-attachment on the ground of self-esteem, and self-control, as indicated by the inverse nature of these correlation relationships.

The factors of potential risk of personal dissonance due to the desire of adolescents to lose subordination will be considered next. First of all, significant correlations indicate that the risk of dissonance emergence in the manifestation of subordination is associated with the stated level of self-subordination in one's own real self-image ($r_s = 0.589$, $p \leq 0.001$), and, accordingly, the inverse significant correlation with the desired level in the ideal self-image ($r_s = -0.196$, $p \leq 0.001$). The following significant relationship of dissonance due to the level of subordination with a similar risk of possible dissonance due to the feeling of dependency ($r_s = 0.393$, $p \leq 0.001$) is also natural, which corresponds to self-dissatisfaction due to the stated current level of dependence manifestation in the real self-image ($r_s = 0.200$, $p \leq 0.001$). Similarly, the risk of personal dissonance emergence due to feelings of subordination is influenced by a significant relationship with the potential threat of dissonance emergence in the sphere of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.354$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is also related to the adolescent's assessment of his level of authoritarianism ($r_s = -0.310$, $p \leq 0.001$), the inverse value of which indicates the desire to get rid of excessive subordination and dependency by increasing his own authoritarianism. Uncertainty about the ability to get rid of excessive subordination creates the adolescent's dissatisfaction with himself, which acquires signs of a tendency to self-blame ($r_s = 0.272$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such self-doubt and potentially threatening or dominant others due to the protective mechanism of projection also causes dissonance due to exacerbation of suspicion ($r_s = 0.265$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is confirmed by the excessive level of suspicion stated in the real self-image ($r_s = 0.222$, $p \leq 0.001$). As a compensatory mechanism, such vulnerability causes a desire to enhance demonstrative self-attitude ($r_s = -0.258$, $p \leq 0.001$) in the eyes of others, the inverse correlation with which indicates a desire to mask internal uncertainty and vigilance by positioning a more favourable image. At the same time, dissatisfaction due to one's own excessive suspicion carries the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of egocentric defence of one's

own boundaries ($r_s = 0.257$, $p \leq 0.001$), which corresponds to the assessment of egocentricity of the current real self-image ($r_s = -0.217 \leq 0.001$), the inverse indicator of which shows the instrumental nature of egocentrism not as an end in itself, but as a tool to promote one's own interests, goals and values. Attention is also drawn to the significant correlation with the risk indicator of personal dissonance in adolescents due to defects of altruism ($r_s = 0.254$, $p \leq 0.001$). This state of affairs can generate significant exacerbations of intrapersonal conflict against the background of personal dissonance ($r_s = 0.233$, $p \leq 0.001$). In such a case, there is a danger of weakening self-control due to reduced ability to self-management ($r_s = -0.197$, $p \leq 0.001$), violation of self-acceptance due to reduced self-attachment ($r_s = -0.181$, $p \leq 0.01$). As a result, the risk of losing self-confidence increases ($r_s = -0.176$, $p \leq 0.01$). This jeopardizes the adolescent's perception of the ability to build harmonious and successful friendly relations, as indicated by the important relationship with the risk indicator of personal dissonance occurrence in the sphere of friendship ($r_s = 0.173$, $p \leq 0.01$).

The next sphere of potential threat of personal dissonance emergence in adolescents is the sphere of authoritarianism, due to the inability, in consequence of its insufficient level, to confidently defend one's own life priorities. First of all, this is confirmed by the inverse correlation with the indicator of the existing level of authoritarian development of the real self-image ($r_s = -0.552$, $p \leq 0.001$), which indicates dissatisfaction with its too low level. As a natural result, this raises fears about being subordinated to more dominant people, which also raises the risk of personal dissonance occurrence in the sphere of subordination ($r_s = 0.354$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is confirmed by the adolescent's feeling of excessive levels of subordination ($r_s = 0.300$, $p \leq 0.001$) in the current self-image. Similarly, the threat of violating one's own boundaries due to flaws in authoritarianism leads to adolescent's dissatisfaction with his own egocentrism ($r_s = -0.246$, $p \leq 0.001$), the inverse value of which indicates a feeling of fear of satisfying his own interests at a sufficient level. This is confirmed by the threat of personal dissonance occurrence due to defects of egocentrism ($r_s = 0.205$, $p \leq 0.001$). This situation can also lead to an exacerbation of the risk of personal dissonance emergence due to exacerbation of suspicion ($r_s = 0.231$, $p \leq 0.001$), as a projection of internal self-doubt ($r_s = -0.228$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such suspicion against the background of uncertainty causes the risk of exacerbation and dissonance in the manifestation of friendship ($r_s = 0.212$, $p \leq 0.001$) in the adolescent, when he begins to fear that he will not be able to successfully build close social ties. As a result, there is a decrease in the

sense of self-worth as an individuality ($r_s = -0.210$, $p \leq 0.001$) and self-attachment ($r_s = -0.190$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such uncertainty prevents the adolescent from positioning a favourable image in the eyes of others, as indicated by the inverse correlation with the indicator of demonstrated self-attitude ($r_s = -0.183$, $p \leq 0.01$). This unproductive position of uncertainty exacerbates the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of self-dependence ($r_s = 0.177$, $p \leq 0.01$), which fully corresponds to the above-mentioned dissatisfaction of the adolescent with his own excessive subordinate position in life. The inability to productively resolve the consequences of such personal dissonance causes tendencies to painful self-blame ($r_s = 0.174$, $p \leq 0.01$). The growing anxiety about the problems of satisfying one's own personal and, in particular, social needs, causes the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of altruism ($r_s = 0.165$, $p \leq 0.01$), which may explain the excessive aggression that adolescents observe in the real self-image ($r_s = -0.160$, $p \leq 0.01$) for the time being.

Another sphere of risk of personal dissonance emergence in adolescents is the subjective feeling of self-dependency, which prevents the assertion of their own autonomy in the process of emancipation. This is confirmed by a significant correlation with the indicator of the currently stated and present feeling of his own dependent state of the self-real image ($r_s = 0.425$, $p \leq 0.001$) in the adolescent. As a natural result, this exacerbates the risk of concomitant personal dissonance occurrence in a close sphere, namely in subordination ($r_s = 0.393$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is confirmed by the excessive level of subordination ($r_s = 0.278$, $p \leq 0.001$) in adolescents' stated real self-image. This feeling of dependency and subordination creates a feeling of threat to independence, which can lead to personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of egocentrism ($r_s = 0.245$, $p \leq 0.001$), as the inability to defend one's own interests against external circumstances and hindering influence of more dominant others. This feeling of self-dependency and weakness generates destructive tendencies to unproductive self-blame ($r_s = 0.232$, $p \leq 0.001$). The consequence of this may result in the emergence of personal dissonance in the sphere of suspicion ($r_s = 0.225$, $p \leq 0.001$) against the background of exacerbation of distrust of oneself and others, which is confirmed by the stated level of acute self-suspicion in the current real self-image ($r_s = 0.154$, $p \leq 0.01$). Due to such a watchful attitude towards oneself and others, there is also a risk of exacerbation of dissonance in the consequence of the inability to build harmonious altruistic relationships with the close social environment ($r_s = 0.220$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is confirmed by the stated existing level of friendship in the real self-image of adolescents ($r_s = 0.186$, $p \leq 0.01$). The inverse correlation of the

demonstrated self-attitude ($r_s = -0.180$, $p \leq 0.01$) indicates difficulties in building a favourable self-image in the eyes of others. Such a feeling of self-dissatisfaction, coming into conflict with real ambitions and aspirations, increases the level of intrapersonal proneness to conflict ($r_s = 0.178$, $p \leq 0.01$). Obsessive thoughts about one's own problems, which arise as a result of excessive dependence, threaten the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.177$, $p \leq 0.01$), as a means of defending one's own life boundaries. This situation creates a feeling of outsiderism in the adolescent, which leads to self-deprecation, neglect of one's own interests, and, as a consequence, reduces self-attachment ($r_s = -0.163$, $p \leq 0.01$).

The factors of personal dissonance having the lowest risks based on their rating follow then. Thus, in particular, the risk of dissonance due to the desire of adolescents to reduce their level of protective aggression is associated primarily with the discrepancy between the ideal self-image of the adolescent ($r_s = -0.287$, $p \leq 0.001$), the inverse correlation with which determines the desire to reduce this quality. Instead, the feeling of excessive manifestation of aggression in the real self-image ($r_s = 0.237$, $p \leq 0.001$) becomes an obstacle to the harmonious socialization of the adolescent. The increase in assertiveness is associated with a natural increase in the risk of relevant personal dissonances in the field of suspicion ($r_s = 0.218$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is explained by the adolescents' feeling of excessive suspicion in the real self-image ($r_s = 0.161$, $p \leq 0.01$). These problems with aggression are reflected in the problems of feelings of friendship ($r_s = 0.194$, $p \leq 0.001$) in relations with the immediate social environment, which is confirmed by the inverse correlation with the indicator of feeling of the current level of friendship development in the adolescent's real self-image ($r_s = -0.158$, $p \leq 0.01$). As a natural result, such dissonance results in a decrease of self-confidence ($r_s = -0.156$, $p \leq 0.01$) due to feelings of insecurity (or inability to defend one's own boundaries).

The next risk of danger is personal dissonance due to adolescents' subjective feeling to satisfy their egocentric desires as a form of defending their independence. Such dissonance, first of all, correlates with the feeling of unrealisation of the possibility of defending one's own present time interests, which is indicated by a significant correlation with the egocentrism indicator of the real self-image ($r_s = -0.311$, $p \leq 0.001$). This can be explained by the feeling of vulnerability due to the risk of dissonance emergence in the feeling of subordination ($r_s = 0.257$, $p \leq 0.001$) and dependency ($r_s = 0.245$, $p \leq 0.001$), which explains the feeling of inability to defend one's own interests and aspirations. This rueful feelings corresponds

to the indicator of the feeling of existing subordination ($r_s = 0.167$, $p \leq 0.01$) to the external dominant circumstances of life situations. This situation of feeling vulnerable causes a risk of personal dissonance due to feelings of distrust of oneself and others as well as suspicion ($r_s = 0.198$, $p \leq 0.001$), the growth of which is supported by the stated level of excessive distrust in the real self-image ($r_s = 0.222$, $p \leq 0.001$). Uncertainty in one's own ability to defend one's own boundaries is associated with the risk of adolescents' personal dissonance emergence in the manifestation of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.205$, $p \leq 0.001$) as a tool of self-affirmation, confirmed by unsatisfactory, from the point of view of the adolescents, level of self-affirmation current status, as indicated by the inverse correlation with the indicator of authoritarianism of the real self-image ($r_s = -0.194$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such a wobbly position reduces the level of self-confidence ($r_s = -0.172$, $p \leq 0.01$), prevents the adolescent from accepting himself ($r_s = -0.162$, $p \leq 0.01$), and impairs the ability to effectively and adequately self-control due to defects in the ability to self-management ($r_s = -0.169$, $p \leq 0.01$).

Now let's move on to the least dangerous, in terms of the risks of personal dissonance emergence, which include spheres of friendship and altruism. These risks may be derived from the above factors, however, can not be ignored, because they determine the productivity of social adaptation of adolescents.

Thus, the risk of personal dissonance emergence due to adolescents' dissatisfaction in the sphere of friendship corresponds to the desire to increase it from the existing level of real self-image ($r_s = -0.199$, $p \leq 0.001$), due to fears about its underdevelopment. Such destructive tendencies are associated with the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of altruism ($r_s = 0.377$, $p \leq 0.001$), which is confirmed by the inverse correlation with the current level of its manifestation ($r_s = -0.197$, $p \leq 0.001$). This indicates the desire of the adolescent to get rid of the problems of establishing friendly relations with a significant close social environment by increasing altruistic behavioural tendencies. The inability to build one's own friendly relations creates anxiety, which can result in the risk of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of mistrust and suspicion ($r_s = 0.258$, $p \leq 0.001$). The risk of destruction of friendly relations can create a danger of personal dissonance emergence in the sphere of authoritarianism, as a deprivation of the ability to build one's own comfortable life boundaries, as indicated by a strong correlation with the indicator of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.212$, $p \leq 0.001$). This tendency is confirmed by dissatisfaction with the existing capacity for emancipation,

which is manifested in the statement by the adolescent of an unsatisfactory level of opportunity to actualize his desirable self-image ($r_s = -0.210$, $p \leq 0.001$). The threat of exacerbation of personal dissonance in the sphere of aggression increases ($r_s = 0.194$, $p \leq 0.001$) in the case of psychotraumatic conditions emergence, not as a destructive tendency, but as a fear of inability to defend one's own aspirations without the inner circle support.

And the last, in terms of the risk of personal dissonances emergence in adolescents, is the danger of their emergence in the sphere of altruistic inclinations, which are generally assessed as in need of development. In particular, personal dissonance in the sphere of altruism is directly related to the risk of a number of interrelated personal dissonances emergence, which should include violations of friendship ($r_s = 0.377$, $p \leq 0.001$). The adolescent, therefore, is wary of establishing close relations of trust on the principle of "peer-to-peer", the reason for which may be the possibility of personal dissonance emergence in the manifestation of subordination ($r_s = 0.254$, $p \leq 0.001$). Such fears can form intolerance to uncertainty, which results in the threat of personal dissonance emergence against the background of exacerbation of suspicion ($r_s = 0.247$, $p \leq 0.001$). This situation can cause the adolescent to feel dissatisfied with his own inability to build harmonious relations on the basis of equality, which can lead to the risk of personal dissonance emergence against the background of feelings of one's own dependency ($r_s = 0.220$, $p \leq 0.001$). A loss of self-confidence may be the consequence of this, as indicated by the inverse correlation ($r_s = -0.192$, $p \leq 0.001$), as well as the weakening of the ability to present oneself in a favourable reputation, as indicated by the inverse correlation with the demonstrated self-attitude ($r_s = -0.169$, $p \leq 0.01$). This situation of subjective feeling of abandonment can lead to personal dissonance emergence against the background of inability to defend one's own aspirations, as indicated by the correlation relationship of the risk of dissonance in the manifestation of authoritarianism ($r_s = 0.165$, $p \leq 0.01$).

4. Limits and Discussion

Based on the research, it can be stated that the emergence of personal dissonances in different spheres of adolescents are interrelated and have a negative impact on the components of the system of their self-attitude.

The risk of personal dissonance in the sphere of suspicion due to the adolescent's desire to reduce it is associated with the indicators of suspicion

of perceived real and ideal self-images, propensity to self-blame, the indicator of subordination in the real self-image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonance by manifestations of subordination, friendship, altruism, authoritarianism, dependency, aggression and egocentrism, the indicator of demonstrated self-attitude, the indicator of the dependency in the real self-image, intrapersonal proneness to conflict, decreased self-confidence, self-attachment and self-management.

The risk of personal dissonance due to the desire of the adolescent to get rid of excessive subordination is associated with the indicators of subordination in one's own real and ideal self-images, the indicators of risk of personal dissonance in terms of manifestation of dependency, authoritarianism, suspicion, egocentrism, altruism and friendship, manifestation of dependency in the real self-image, the indicator of the authoritarianism in the real self-image, tendency to self-blame, the indicator of suspicion in the real self-image, the desire to increase demonstrated self-attitude in the eyes of others, the indicator of egocentrism in the real self-image, increased intrapersonal proneness to conflict, weakened self-control and self-management, decreased self-attachment, loss of self-confidence.

The risk of personal dissonance in the field of authoritarianism, due to the inability and in the consequence of its insufficient level, to confidently defend one's own life priorities is associated with the indicator of authoritarianism in the self-real image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonances in terms of the manifestations of subordination, egocentrism, suspicion, friendship, dependency and altruism, the level of subordination in the real self-image, the manifestation of egocentrism in the real self-image, self-doubt, decreased self-worth and self-attachment, weakened demonstrated self-attitude, increased tendency to self-blame, the indicator of aggression in the real self-image.

The risk of personal dissonance due to the adolescent's feelings of self-dependence, which prevents the assertion of his own autonomy in the process of emancipation, is associated with the indicator of dependent state in the real self-image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonances in terms of the manifestation of subordination, egocentrism, suspicion, altruism and authoritarianism, the indicator of subordination in the real self-image, tendency to unproductive self-blame, the indicator of suspicion in the real self-image, the indicator of friendship in the real self-image, decreased demonstrated self-attitude, increased interpersonal proneness to conflict, decreased self-attachment.

The risk of personal dissonance due to the desire of the adolescent to reduce his level of protective aggression is associated with decreased

aggression in the ideal self-image against the background of its inflated level in the real self-image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonance in terms of the manifestation of suspicion and friendship, the indicator of excessive suspicion in the real self-image, the indicator of friendship in the real self-image, decreased self-confidence.

The risk of personal dissonance due to the subjective feeling of adolescents' inability to satisfy their egocentric desires as forms of defending their independence, is associated with the indicator of egocentrism in the real self-image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonances in terms of the manifestations of subordination, dependency, suspicion and authoritarianism, the indicator of subordination in the real self-image, the indicator of suspicion in the real self-image, decreased manifestation of authoritarianism in the real self-image, decreased self-confidence, difficulties in self-acceptance, deterioration of self-management.

The risk of personal dissonance due to the adolescents' dissatisfaction in the sphere of friendship is associated with weakened level of friendship in the real self-image, the indicators of risk of personal dissonances in terms of the manifestation of altruism, suspicion, authoritarianism and aggression, reduced altruism in the real self-image, manifestation of aggression in the ideal self-image.

The risk of personal dissonance of the adolescent in the field of altruistic inclinations is associated with the indicators of risk of personal dissonances in terms of the manifestations of friendship, subordination, suspicion, dependency and authoritarianism, loss of self-confidence, weakened demonstrated self-attitude.

The results of our research complement the findings of many scientists (Aleksandrov, et al., 2017; Boriak et al., 2021; Bridges et al., 2004; Ding & Kalashnyk, 2020; Gratz et al., 2010; Mannapova et al., 2020) and expand them.

5. Conclusions

On the basis of the comparative analysis of the profiles of the ideal and the real self-images of adolescents it was found that the greatest discrepancy between self-images is observed in terms of suspicion, subordination, authoritarianism and dependency. It should be noted that the correlation analysis also showed the largest number of significant relationships in the indicators of dissonance in the sphere of suspicion (17), subordination (18), authoritarianism (15) and dependency (13). This is where a significant source of dissonance can lie, because it is these qualities that

adolescents want to change the most in themselves. Less pronounced are the discrepancies between the real and the ideal self-image in terms of aggression and egocentrism. These qualities, although weak, but are still pronounced, and therefore can also be considered a potential source of self-dissatisfaction, and, consequently, albeit small, but still, the risk of dissonance. And the least pronounced are the discrepancies in the sphere of friendship and altruism, which indicates sufficient satisfaction of adolescents with the current level of development of these qualities.

The correlation analysis confirmed that the emergence of dissonances in different spheres of adolescents are interrelated and have a negative impact on the components of their self-attitude system. Therefore, these factors require priority attention in the implementation of psychoprophylaxis and psychological correction of personal dissonances of adolescents in the process of psychological care organization.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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